

RI-VIS - Second outreach and partnering event

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Executive Summary

The Latin America-Europe Symposium on Research Infrastructures was organised by the RI-VIS and EU-LAC ResInfra projects, and brought together delegates from Latin American and European research infrastructures (RIs), science policy organisations and research institutions to discuss opportunities and challenges for RI cooperation between Latin America and Europe.

International cooperation in science and technology is an important part of addressing major global issues like climate change, infectious diseases, food security, and natural disasters. RIs are organisations, which provide access to state-of-the-art technologies, resources, services and expertise to scientists.

The RI-VIS project consortium consists of RIs across scientific disciplines to work together more efficiently and to increase their visibility among the scientific user community, global RIs and science policy organisations. RIs provide such coordination by offering a transparent access procedure to key facilities, resources and expertise on the basis of scientific excellence. They empower research beyond the individual research capacity of different countries, economic sectors, or institutions. We invited representatives from scientific communities, RI operational staff, funding agencies as well as policy makers to join and discuss opportunities for working together with the aim to bring together the right people to create collaborations and initiate networks for the benefit of all stakeholders.

The RI-VIS and EU-LAC ResInfra projects share common goals to build sustainable partnerships in research infrastructure between Europe and Latin America and the Caribbean.

Detailed report on the deliverable

Background/Introduction

Research infrastructures (RIs) across scientific domains joined forces as part of the RI-VIS project (<https://ri-vis.eu/>) in order to work together more efficiently to increase their visibility in Europe and other world regions among their varied stakeholders.

RI-VIS aims to increase the international visibility of European RIs outside Europe and share the experience and expertise accrued in the various areas as building blocks for other regions to initiate and optimize infrastructural activities. Therefore, the goal of WP3 on Global Outreach and Partnering Events is to increase the visibility of the activities and developments, organize thematic events bringing together relevant European and international players to initiate and/or strengthen collaboration opportunities. This is being achieved, among other things, through transparent and active communication within the community of European RIs, and coordinated intensive external communications with existing or aspiring research infrastructures and their stakeholders in the partner international region. RI-VIS addresses a specific need for outreach events to promote research infrastructures globally. The project complements and cooperates with other initiatives, as illustrated by this Latin America-Europe Symposium on Research Infrastructures, which is co-organised by Ri-VIS and the EU-LAC ResInfra project.

The Latin America-Europe Symposium on Research Infrastructures was organised by the RI-VIS and EU-LAC ResInfra projects, and brought together delegates from Latin American and European RIs,

science policy organisations and research institutions to discuss opportunities and challenges for RI cooperation between Latin America and Europe.

Description of work

The “Latin America-Europe Symposium on Research Infrastructures” is the second event in a series of three international symposia, which are organised as part of the RI-VIS project. This symposium was co-organised by RI-VIS project and the EU-LAC ResInfra project (<https://resinfra-eulac.eu/>), a Horizon 2020-funded project, which strives towards a new EU-LAC partnership in Research Infrastructures. Both projects share common goals to build sustainable partnerships between RIs in Europe and Latin America and the Caribbean.

The aim of this three-day symposium was to raise awareness of the different research infrastructure initiatives in Latin America and Europe and to discuss opportunities to initiate new or strengthen existing bi-regional cooperation.

This symposium was originally organised as an in-person meeting in the Center for Research in Energy and Materials (CNPEM) in Campinas, Brazil on October 22-23, 2020, with the kind support by Dora Maria Marques (Events-Communication Advisory) and Ana Carolina de Mattos Zeri (Manaca Beamline Coordinator). CNPEM is located in Campinas, Sao Paulo state in Brazil, and it houses four world-class laboratories, which are open to the scientific community: the Synchrotron Light National Laboratory (LNLS); the Biosciences National Laboratory (LNBio); the Biorenewables National Laboratory (LNBR) and the Nanotechnology National Laboratory (LNNano). Due to the ongoing COVID-19 pandemic and travel restrictions, the organisers decided to re-organise the symposium as a digital event on June 14-17, 2021.

As mentioned in D3.1, the main advantages of organising the Latin America-Europe Symposium as a digital event are the ability to reach out to a larger audience as well as the opportunity to have speakers and attendees from across Latin America, Europe and other countries. No travel was necessary to join the symposium, so the time commitment for speakers, attendees and panellists, especially for those from overseas, was significantly reduced. Also, from an environmental perspective, the carbon footprint is reduced compared to an in-person meeting. To enable this participation from a very broad geographical distribution of participants, the event schedule was optimised to accommodate participants from Mexico to Eastern Europe, with the main symposium running from 10:30-14:00 UTC-3 (Campinas time) each day.

Latin America - Europe Symposium
on Research Infrastructures

15-17 June 2021

UTC-3 / BRT / UYT / ART 10 11 12 13 14 15 16 17 18

UTC-5 / CDT / COT 8 9 10 11 12 13 14 15 16

UTC+1 / BST 14 15 16 17 18 19 20 21 22

UTC+2 / CEST 15 16 17 18 19 20 21 22 23

RI-VIS

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Networking and personal communication with other attendees at an in-person conference is an important aspect when discussing and initiating new collaborations and exchanging experiences. Many of these discussions take place during coffee breaks and social dinners. In-person events are also often combined with site visits of local RIs, universities and research institutes as well as with poster sessions, where individual (also early-career) scientists and potential RI users can present their research. Unfortunately, the direct personal interactions cannot be easily replicated by online symposia.

During the previous ‘Africa-Europe Symposium on Research Infrastructures’, we have therefore tried and tested several online tools and platforms for facilitating and supporting the exchange and interaction between the symposium participants in an online format. Many of these successful tools were also used for the Latin America – Europe Symposium on Research Infrastructures. In addition to informing interested colleagues about this symposium via the RI-VIS project website (<https://ri-vis.eu/network/rivis/events/ri-vis-latin-america---europe-symposium-1>), a dedicated symposium platform (<https://whova.com/>) was used, which offers additional features for the participants before and during the symposium: the attendees were invited to prepare their own 'attendee profile' with their information e.g. name, affiliation, position and a short bio-sketch, and these profiles were accessible to other attendees. The attendees could also contact other attendees directly and send them in-app messages. If they wished to initiate a larger discussion and engage with a broader audience, the attendees could initiate a discussion in the 'community' area by adding a topic or social group. Furthermore, attendees could propose meet-ups and 'virtual meets' and discuss in smaller groups through videoconferencing. The organisers could be contacted by attendees and receive their questions and suggestions through the event platform. Handouts, flyers, brochures and other documents were shared on the event platform, and presentations and longer documents were uploaded in the 'handout' area. Whova also has a section to share pictures (60 photos have been shared by attendees) and attendees had the opportunity to share comments.

After the positive feedback from the attendees of the ‘Africa-Europe Symposium on RIs’ on the opportunity to showcase individual RIs as part of a “virtual exhibition”, we invited RIs and other initiatives to exhibit their work in the same format during the Latin America-Europe Symposium. Through these virtual booths (14 in total), the RIs could share videos, handouts, marketing content, photos, and even live showcases so that other attendees could learn more about the exhibiting RIs, how to engage with them and what they offer, throughout the symposium. In addition, RI exhibitors could interact directly with the attendees using the chat function of the symposium platform. Once attendees contact the respective RI or request more info, they are able to automatically receive their information.

Networking online cannot replace the physical networking of an in-person meeting, but some dedicated online networking tools (e.g., <https://www.wonder.me/>) promise to offer an organic networking experience and allow attendees to network with the other attendees in an authentic way online. During the networking session, the attendees were invited to join the online networking area and they have full autonomy of who they can speak to by moving their avatar around. The attendees can look for other participants they would like to meet and chose who to talk to and when. When they approach another person, or join a group of people, a virtual room automatically opens, and they can directly start the conversation and network. Specific themes can be assigned to these virtual ‘bubbles’ in order to attract other like-minded people, who are also interested in the same topic. These bubbles can also be locked if attendees prefer to have an undisturbed conversation, for example, on confidential project ideas. At the same time, messages and invitations to join a specific conversation can be sent to other attendees. A participant list helped the attendees to locate other attendees in the room. The number of participants joining the networking session was similar to that during the first event with approximately 20 participants. The engagement in the networking session may have been reduced by the challenge of working across diverse time zones as the networking activity took place after the symposium close which was late evening for those joining from central Europe.

In addition to the presentations, panel discussions, networking session, thematic workshops (which will be described below) and virtual exhibitions, a virtual site visit was organised. The first day of the symposium was concluded with a “Sirius virtual visit – a live tour through one of the most advanced synchrotron light sources in the world”, hosted by Ana Zeri, coordinator of the beamline Manacá, and Florian Meneau, coordinator of the beamline Cateretê. During the virtual tour, the symposium participants had the opportunity to virtually visit the CATERETÊ (Coherent And TimE RESolved ScatTERing) beamline, which provides unique capabilities in biological and soft materials imaging and dynamics experiments with a particular focus on the application of coherent X-ray scattering and diffraction techniques, and MANACÁ (MACromolecular micro and NAnoCrystAllography), which will be the first macromolecular crystallography beamline of Sirius and optimized for micrometric and sub-micrometric focus. The virtual visitors learnt that the project includes two experimental stations, including beams with dimensions of 0.5×0.5 micrometres (nano station) and 10×7 a 100×80 micrometres (micro station), dedicated to studying three-dimensional structures of macromolecules, particularly complex arrangements such as viruses, membrane proteins and protein complexes and ligands.

Representatives from Latin American and European research infrastructure initiatives, funding organisations as well as independent scientists who are interested in using these RIs for their own research projects, were among the speakers, panellists and participants. We had excellent speakers from 13 countries representing research organisations, policymakers and RIs, from the life sciences-sciences to environmental, physical and social sciences.

The Director of Brazilian Synchrotron Light Laboratory, Harry Westfahl Jr. delivered the welcome speech. After the opening and welcome speech, Inmaculada Figueroa, Deputy Vice-Director General for Internationalisation of Science and Innovation, Ministry of Science & Innovation (MICINN), Spain, and Vice-Chair of the European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures (ESFRI); and Fernando Amestoy, Presidente del Polo Científico y Tecnológico de Pando, Uruguay set the scene of the symposium during the 'Research Infrastructure landscapes in Latin America and Europe' session.

After a presentation by Dominik Sobczak, European Commission Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, Susan Daenke, Instruct-ERIC and Coordinator of the RI-VIS project, presented the 'RI-VIS project - Increasing the visibility of European research infrastructures and facilitating new partnerships', followed by a presentation of the 'EU-LAC ResInfra project – Towards a new EU-LAC partnership in Research Infrastructures' by Inmaculada Figueroa during the session 'Creating synergies – Towards new EU-LAC RI partnerships'.

Successful case studies of multinational and biregional Latin American-European partnerships were highlighted in a dedicated session. The speakers presented case studies of multinational and biregional Latin American-European partnerships in structural biology; the International Consortium for Personalised Medicine (ICPerMed); Embrapa (Empresa Brasileira de Pesquisa Agropecuária); the E-Science European Infrastructure for Biodiversity and Ecosystem Research LifeWatch ERIC; and case studies of multinational and biregional Latin American-European partnerships in the field of imaging.

During the three days of the symposium, individual RIs from Latin America and Europe presented their initiatives, their service offers, cooperation opportunities or ongoing biregional partnerships and collaborative projects during the 'Expanding Latin American-European partnerships - New Opportunities' session. This session included presentations on CNPEM (Brazilian Center for Research in Energy and Materials) and its 4 national labs: LNBio (biosciences), LNLS (synchrotron), LNBR (bio-renewables), LNNano (nano technologies); the European RI for biobanking (BBMRI); the European RI in Chemical Biology and Early Drug Discovery (EU-OPENSREEN); CCMAR, the Portuguese node of the European Marine Biological Resource Centre EMBRC; Laboratorio de Encuestas y Análisis Social [LEAS], Universidad Adolfo Ibáñez; Iberian-American Network for High Performance Computing (RICAP); European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science (E-RIHS); and RedCLARA: Latin American Cooperation of Advanced Networks.

These talks were complemented by a presentation on the 'EMBL Technology Developers Programme: ARISE – Career Accelerator for Research Infrastructure Scientists' and an announcement of the upcoming International Conference on Research Infrastructures (ICRI) 2022.

Two panel discussions were organised on June 16th and 17th. During the first panel discussion, which was chaired by Sven Fahrner, EMPHASIS, the panellists Alberto Majo, Ministry of Education, Culture and Science, Uruguay; Andres Triana, Director of Research Networks and Scientific Infrastructure, and Consejo Nacional de Ciencia y Tecnología (CONACYT), Mexico; Federico Torres-Carballo, Ministerio de Ciencia, Tecnología y Telecomunicaciones (MICITT), Costa Rica; María Natalia Lisa, Instituto de Biología Molecular y Celular de Rosario (IBR-CONICET-UNR), Argentina; and Patricia Postigo McLaughlin, EU Commission discussed 'Opportunities for Latin American-European collaborations between RIs'.

During the second panel discussion, chaired by Susan Daenke, Instruct-ERIC, the panellists Andres Lopez, Head of the Equipment and Infrastructure Department, National Research and Development Agency, ANID, Chile; Inmaculada Figueroa, Vice Deputy Director General, Internationalisation of Science and Innovation, Ministry of Science & Innovation, Spain; Damian Refojo, Neuroscience Department, Instituto de Investigación en Biomedicina de Buenos Aires (IBioBA), CONICET Partner Institute of the Max Planck Society, Argentina; Manoel Barral, Fiocruz, Brazil; Lelio Fellows Filho, International Affairs Unit, CNPq, Brazil; Raquel Hurtado-Ortiz, CNCM - Institut Pasteur, France discussed the 'Future of Latin America-Europe Research Infrastructure Collaborations'. During both panel discussions, attendees were invited to contribute to the discussion by submitting questions and comments or by commenting on the statements of the panellists. The multitude of submitted questions and animated discussions among the panellists during the panel discussions are testament to the engagement and active participation of the attendees. The interactive debate demonstrated the importance of the discussed topics and the high motivation of scientists in Latin America and Europe to work more closely together and foster cooperation between Latin America and European RIs in the future. One important conclusion was the need for dedicated funding opportunities and frameworks to support these biregional collaboration between RIs. The EU is ready to support cooperation by developing bilateral R&I roadmaps with priority on non-EU countries and the Horizon Europe programme is more open with strategically targeted actions.

Prior to the symposium, RI-VIS (WP2) consulted experts from different scientific domains and on all career levels from both Europe and Latin America, who represent RIs in Latin America and Europe as well as policy makers and have outstanding experience with such RI collaboration. A white paper [1], which was published before the symposium and shared with the speakers, panellists and participants, assembled the insights of the experts and presented key recommendations for RI representatives, policy makers and funding organisations to facilitate Latin American-European RI partnerships. The report also highlights examples of successful Latin American-European RI collaboration, best practices for successful collaboration, and current challenges and bottlenecks. One of the recommendations of the white paper is that *"European RIs should place more emphasis on outreach activities in Latin America"*. By organising the Latin America-Europe RI Symposium, RI-VIS has already started to address this recommendation. Organising this symposium jointly with the EU-LAC ResInfra project addressed another recommendation of the white paper: *"Getting involved with initiatives that promote bi-regional collaboration, such as EU-LAC ResInfra (EU-LAC ResInfra, 2019) or EULAC-PerMed (EULAC PerMed, 2019), have proven effective as a means to connect RIs."*

The first RI-VIS symposium was originally planned to be held in South Africa and the third symposium will focus on Australia, so the majority of speakers and participants of both symposia were (or will be) native English speakers. The majority of the speakers and attendees of the Latin America-Europe Symposium, however, are native Spanish speakers, with the exception of those from Brazil. In order to facilitate lively discussions, simultaneous interpretation from English to Spanish and vice-versa by three native-speaking experts was offered. The web conference tool offered a feature to include interpreters in the live meeting to enable language interpretation. By so doing, the interpreters provided their own audio channels for the language they are translating to (English and Spanish). Attendees could then select the audio channel to hear the translated audio in their language of choice, as well as the option to mute the original audio instead of hearing it in a lower volume with their chosen language (<https://support.zoom.us/hc/en-us/articles/360034919791-Translating-your-meeting-or-webinar>). The speakers and panellists (and probably many attendees) made ample use of the simultaneous interpretation and they confirmed that this feature was very helpful to enable lively discussions among the attendees throughout the sessions. The organisers of this symposium agreed

that the benefits of the simultaneous translation cannot be understated, and recommend that this option should be seriously considered by organisers of similar events where the majority of speakers and participants are not native speakers of the official language of the event.

WP3 took care of the setup of the platform and to integrate all the elements needed to the optimal operation of the event. Below the landing page of the event:

The participation in this event was for free, but registration was mandatory. The registration was opened on March 8th, 2021. There was a total of 614 registrations and 14 virtual booths were set-up. From these 614 registrations, 419 participants (including speakers) attended the symposium from Latin America, Europe and other regions.

It was an explicit aim to have a geographical balance and to attract a similar number of attendees from Latin America and Europe, respectively. We made use of local networks of RI-VIS and EU-LAC ResInfra partners to reach out to speakers and to raise awareness about the symposium among the scientific community in Latin America. As shown in the pie chart below, >50% of the attendees came from the target region of this symposium (ie. Latin America). This geographical balance among the symposium attendees facilitated the discussions between RIs and their respective counterparts in the other world region, and built trust among potential future partners:

The engagement of the attendees was high, as demonstrated by the following statistics:

In comparison with the first RI-VIS outreach and partnering event, which focused on Africa-Europe RI collaborations, the engagement of the attendees was higher at the LAC-EU symposium. For example, >800 messages have been sent by attendees (>250 at the first symposium), 33 community board topic posted (22 at first symposium), 92 photos taken (52 at first symposium) and >400 App downloads (200 at the first event).

Engagement with the symposium via social media was also strong. Twitter analytics from the @RI_VIS_eu Twitter account show that over the three days of the event, @RI_VIS_eu tweets received over 21,000 impressions each day with an average engagement rate of 1.2%.

After the event, a survey was distributed among the attendees, and the results are compiled in this document (Annex 2). The feedback from participants regarding the event platform was overall positive, with the features of the online symposium platform to network and the variety among the speakers and the institutions/research infrastructures that represented were specifically highlighted. The take-home message from the attendees was the opportunity to learn about the existing networks and the opportunity to create new ones.

Note: The picture was shared on Twitter with the consent of the attendees featured.

In conjunction with the main symposium, several RIs organized four thematic satellite events: (i) Instruct ERIC; (ii) BBMRI-ERIC, together with European, Middle Eastern & African Society for Biopreservation and Biobanking (ESBB); (iii) MIRRI; and (iv) Euro-Biolmaging, Latin America Bioimaging and Global Biolmaging.

Instruct-ERIC organised the satellite event, “Strengthening the Structural Biology Community in Latin America”, which took place on 16 June. The workshop covered a range of sessions: Latin America Structural Biology Landscape Analysis, Examples of Latin American Research Infrastructures, Models for Integration Between Regions, and finally a panel discussion between speakers. The event had 122

participants from 20 countries, with more than 70% joining from Latin America. The workshop provided a platform for structural biologists to understand what is available for their research in both regions, as well as highlight to policy makers what is needed.

BBMRI-ERIC organised the workshop: Prerequisites for biobanking collaborations and advancements across continents, together with European, Middle Eastern & African Society for Biopreservation and Biobanking (ESBB), instructed the participants on “How to build a biobank” and “Pre-analytics and Quality”, with time for questions and answers. The 30 participants to the workshop were engaged and interested in learning from their experiences. This workshop gave the opportunity to reconnect with policy makers, researchers and biobankers for future collaborations.

MIRRI organized, under the IS_MIRRI21 project, two information and matchmaking events dedicated to Horizon Europe opportunities and MIRRI membership. The webinar “MIRRI Membership: Boosting research and innovation in Health, Agro-food, Environment and Energy” aimed to bring the added-value of MIRRI to light and to encourage international cooperation among Research Infrastructures in Europe and Latin America, as well as to briefly present funding opportunities that are available under the Horizon Europe Pillar 1 to facilitate that cooperation. The workshop “International collaboration with MIRRI through new opportunities from the Horizon Europe programme” aimed to provide an overview of the opportunities presented in Horizon Europe Pillar 2 that correlate to the domains of MIRRI (Health & Food, Agro-Food, and Environment & Energy), to give an overview of MIRRI’s Strategic Research & Innovation Agenda 2021-2030, and to formulate synergies among different innovation actors in the above-mentioned domains with the aim of jointly pursuing relevant Horizon Europe calls. More information can be found here: https://ismirri21.mirri.org/2021/06/23/successful-launch-and-completion-of-is_mirri21-mirri-two-matchmaking-events/.

Euro-Biolmaging ERIC, Latin America Bioimaging and Global Bioimaging co-organised the satellite event entitled “Latin America Bioimaging network: facts, experiences and challenges”, which took place on June 18th and saw the participation of almost 100 participants from 15 countries. The workshop explored how the lessons learned from community and infrastructure building in Europe could support the strengthening of Latin America Bioimaging, a newly created network that brings together researchers, service providers, educators and commercial technology integrators in bioimaging across Latin America. More information about the event can be found on the Latin America Bioimaging website (<http://latambioimaging.org/index.php/satellite-meeting-june-2021>) and the presentations delivered can be watched on the Latin America Bioimaging YouTube Channel (https://www.youtube.com/playlist?list=PLfc37rKFmbJQZlXBGnsJ_ohDRTzClu-sD)

Conclusion/Next steps

The symposium was a very successful event. According to the responses of the post-event survey, the participants, panellists, speakers and project partners were satisfied with the outcome, the platform and content. It was highly appreciated by the attendees and project partners to have scientists as well as funders and policy makers in the same (virtual) place, the exchange of ideas sparked some interesting dialogues and laid the groundwork for future collaborations.

The symposium attracted a high number of registrations (614, excluding speakers) and attendees that joined the symposium (>400). The majority of the attendees came from Latin American countries. Simultaneous translation (English-Spanish) was offered to the attendees, speakers and panellist, which facilitated the lively discussions between the symposium participants.

Due to the different time zones in Latin America and Europe, the symposium was spread over three shorter days, as compared to two (full) days for the previous Africa-Europe symposium, with Europe and Africa sharing similar time zones.

Virtual events cannot replicate the experience of in-person meetings, and the opportunity to network with other attendees is limited in an online format. In order to mitigate this challenge, several online tools were used, which facilitated the active participation of and networking between the symposium attendees. The different formats, e.g. presentations, panel discussions, thematic workshops, networking sessions, ensured that the sessions were engaging and that attendees could actively contribute to the discussions throughout the symposium. This observation was corroborated by the results of the post-event survey and discussions between the organisers and participants.

A highlight of the symposium was the ‘Sirius virtual visit – a live tour through one of the most advanced synchrotron light sources in the world’, which allowed the participants to remotely experience a virtual visit of the beamline in Campinas, Brazil.

The sessions were recorded, taking into account the speakers’ consent, and uploaded to the RI-VIS YouTube channel and to the Whova platform.

The positive feedback from the attendees and the experience with the overall programme structure, agenda topics, session formats, online platform and networking support will be very valuable for the organisation of the upcoming (third) symposium, the Australia-Europe Symposium on Research Infrastructures, which will be held on October 5-7, 2021.

References

- [1] L. Vincenz-Donnelly, S. Fahrner, G. Pahlavan, P. Garcia, R. Pieruschka, C. Alén Amaro, B. Stechmann, A. Buschiazio, I. Figueroa and M. Kim, “Recommendations towards cooperation between Latin American and European research infrastructures,” *Zenodo*, p. <https://zenodo.org/record/4544374>, 2021.

Appendices

Latin America - Europe Symposium on Research Infrastructures

#LatinAmericaEURResearchInfra

Virtual partnering event

*Times are given in UTC-3 = CDT+2 = CEST-5

15 June 2021

- *10:30 Opening and welcome of participants
Jose Roque - Director of Brazilian Center for Research in Energy and Materials (CNPEM), Campinas, Brazil
- 10:45 Research Infrastructure landscapes in Latin America and Europe
Inmaculada Figueroa - Ministry of Science & innovation, Spain; and Vice-Chair of the European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures (ESFRI)
Fernando Amestoy - Presidente del Polo Científico y Tecnológico de Pando, Uruguay
- 11:25 Creating synergies – Towards new EU-LAC RI partnerships
European Commission
The RI-VIS Project - *Susan Daenke*, Instruct-ERIC; and Coordinator of the RI-VIS project, Oxford, UK
EU-LAC ResInfra Project - *Inmaculada Figueroa*
- 12:15 Case studies of multinational and biregional Latin American-European partnerships
Case studies of multinational and biregional Latin American-European partnerships - *Kleber Gomes Franchini*, Director of Brazilian Biosciences National Laboratory (LNBio), Center for Research in Energy and Materials (CNPEM), Campinas, Brazil
The International Consortium for Personalised Medicine (ICPerMed) - *Manoel Barral Neto*, Fundação Oswaldo Cruz (Fiocruz), Rio de Janeiro, Brazil
European Infrastructure for Plant Phenotyping (EMPHASIS) - *Dr Guy de Capdeville*, Director of R&D at EMBRAPA, Brazil
The E-Science European Infrastructure for Biodiversity and Ecosystem Research LifeWatch ERIC - *Juan Miguel González-Aranda*, LifeWatch ERIC
Global-BiImaging - *Chris Wood*, National Laboratory for Advanced Microscopy, Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México (UNAM), Mexico City, Mexico
- 13:30 Wrap up of Day One
Inmaculada Figueroa

16 June 2021

- 10:30 Expanding Latin American-European partnerships - New Opportunities
CNPEM and its 4 national labs: LNBio (biosciences), LNLS (synchrotron), LNBR (bio-renewables), LNNano (nano technologies) - *Jose Roque*, Director of Brazilian Center for Research in Energy and Materials (CNPEM), Campinas, Brazil
The European research infrastructure for biobanking (BBMRI) - *Jens Habermann*, BBMRI ERIC, Austria
EU-OPENSREEN: The European Research Infrastructure in Chemical Biology and Early Drug Discovery - *Bahne Stechmann*, EU-OPENSREEN ERIC, Berlin, Germany
CCMAR, the Portuguese node of the European Marine Biological Resource Centre, EMBRC - *Adelino Canario*, Director of CCMAR, Portugal
- 11:30 Panel discussion: Opportunities for Latin American-European collaborations between RIs
Sven Fahrner, Alberto Majo, Andres Triana, Federico Torres-Carballo, Maria Natalia Lisa
- 13:30 Wrap up of Day Two
Sven Fahrner
- 14:00 Matchmaking activities and thematic workshops

17 June 2021

- 10:30 Expanding Latin American-European partnerships - New Opportunities
Building a probability-based panel to track social change in Chile: lessons, challenges and opportunities - *Ricardo González T.*, Laboratorio de Encuestas y Análisis Social (LEAS), Universidad Adolfo Ibáñez, Santiago, Chile
Iberian-American Network for High Performance Computing (RICAP) - *Rafael Mayo Garcia*, Centro de Investigaciones Medioambientales y Tecnológicas (CIEMAT), Spain
European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science (E-RIHS) - *Sorin Hermon*, Chair of the IPERION HS DIGILAB Working Group and director of STARLAB at the Cyprus Institute (Cyl)
RedCLARA: Latin American Cooperation of Advanced Networks - *Luis Eliécer*, Executive Director of RedCLARA
- 11:30 International Conference on Research Infrastructures (ICRI) 2022
Ondrej Hradil, Research Infrastructures Manager, Masaryk University, Czech Republic
- 11:35 EMBL Technology Developers Programme: ARISE
Tanja Ninkovic, ARISE Program Manager - EMBL
- 11:45 Panel discussion: Future of Latin America-Europe Research Infrastructure Collaborations
Susan Daenke, Andrés López Lara, Lelio Fellows Filho, Inmaculada Figueroa, Damian Refojo, Manoel Barral-Netto, Raquel Hurtado-Ortiz
- 13:45 Conclusions from the Latin America-Europe symposium and Closing Remarks

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<https://bit.ly/latinamerica-europe>

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Appendix 2: Post-event survey results

Timestamp	Country of residence	Please comment on what you liked about the symposium and your recommendations on what could be improved?	Overall, did the sessions meet your expectations?	Which session did you like in particular?	How valuable were the networking opportunities?	Did the symposium structure give ample time to interact with other attendees?	Are you interested in a follow-up symposium in the future?	Would you recommend the symposium to others?	How well organized was the conference?	How would you rate the Whova app?	What are your key take-home messages from this symposium?	Did you make use of the live interpretation services at the conference?	If you used the interpretation service how would you rate it?
16/06/2021 14:49:00	Brazil	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Topics presentations and discussions extremely relevant for the symposium objectives Excellent presentations The event platform, with interesting resources to promote interaction among participants 	Yes	Research infrastructure landscapes in Latin America and Europe	Extremely	Yes	Yes	Yes	Extremely	Excellent	Science need more events like this, where there are spaces for discussions about resources, partnerships so one can accomplish more with the collaboration with partners, than trying everything by itself. Everyone – countries, governments, research bodies, groups and individuals – can benefit from interactions, exchange of ideas and proposals for collaborations.		
16/06/2021 19:33:00	COLOMBIA	great opportunity to networking.	Yes	Case studies of multinational and bregional Latin American-European partnerships	Very	Yes	Yes	Yes	Very	Good	How does my institution could be part of this networks?		
16/06/2021 20:20:00	Brazil	I liked the information of each institution. The work through years and the current situation of the networks.	Yes	About bio imaging and the tour on the synchrotron. Loved these.	Extremely	Yes	Yes	Yes	Extremely	Excellent	I learned too much. Please continue with this type of event. The next O hope good results of new networkings		
17/06/2021 11:42:00	Colombia	I'm very impressive and I liked a lot the event. May be it is necessary to realize more diffusion because it is an important subject for the communities in academia.	Yes	Research infrastructures landscapes and creating synergies ... two excellent sessions.	Extremely	Yes	Yes	Yes	Extremely	Excellent	It is necessary to continue and to expand this type of symposiums in the region.	No, I did not listen to the interpretation	I did not use the interpretation service
17/06/2021 12:05:00	Canada	I liked the topics and also tried to wake up much early to attend those as in my time zone it was 5:00am but unfortunately could not attend as there was no English translation/cc for any of the sessions. I could attend only 1 session from EMBL and liked it. Wish we could get recording of sessions with English translation so I could get caught up.	No	EMBL arise was the only one I could attend and liked it.	Somewhat	No	Yes	Yes	Somewhat	Good	<p>Somy cannot say much but I imagine it was to better understand RI ecosystem, best practices and build collaborations in Latin America and Europe.</p> <p>I am not aware of English interpretation of sessions or the recording that I see following questions. Please share the links.</p>	No, I did not listen to the interpretation	I did not use the interpretation service
17/06/2021 13:07:00	Brazil	It could be improved implement as a booth to see the opportunities of training for example	Yes	Panel discussion: Future of Latin America-Europe Research Infrastructure Collaborations	Extremely	Yes	Yes	Yes	Extremely	Excellent	The networks are very important, we are a citizen of the world.	Yes, I listened to the interpretation in English and Spanish	Excellent
17/06/2021 13:38:00	Slovenia	Excellent presentations and possibilities for networking. Great online platform too.	Yes	Due to my expertise in the field, I found very interesting the workshop "Strengthening the Structural Biology Community in Latin America", thus giving us the opportunity to establish new collaborations.	Extremely	Yes	Yes	Yes	Extremely	Excellent	Excellent symposium that emphasized the scientific collaboration between EU and Latin America.	No, I did not listen to the interpretation	I did not use the interpretation service
17/06/2021 13:56:00	Costa Rica	It is important to share all the capacities that are already in place in different countries and the possibility to share and collaborate.	Yes	The ones with labs and equipments in general. INFRA/ERIC	Very	No	Yes	Yes	Extremely	Excellent	Hubs and collaboration!	No, I did not listen to the interpretation	I did not use the interpretation service
17/06/2021 13:58:00	Argentina	A very neat updated review of research infrastructure available in Europe and also in LAC. It is obvious the strong will to strengthen the collaborations and joint endeavors together aiming for a more efficient synergy. Future looks brighter, although initiatives still depend mainly on funding...	Yes	Future of Latin America-Europe Research Infrastructure Collaborations and Virtual tours	Very	Yes	Yes	Yes	Extremely	Very good	There is strong will to strengthen the collaborations and joint endeavors regarding Research Infrastructure and open access.	No, I did not listen to the interpretation	I did not use the interpretation service
17/06/2021 14:09:00	Brazil	Excellent organization and presentations	Yes	Prerequisites for biobanking collaborations and advancements across continents	Very	Yes	Yes	Yes	Extremely	Very good	Best practices in infrastructure		
17/06/2021 14:16:00	Italy	I liked the friendship atmosphere and competence of speakers. I wot start with a better networking	Yes	The last one	Extremely	No	Yes	Yes	Very	Good	Share experiences, build together EU LAC Space	No, I did not listen to the interpretation	I did not use the interpretation service
18/06/2021 07:50:00	United Kingdom	The symposium provided a great opportunity to learn about initiative for collaboration between the two continents and to plan future ones.	Yes	The Structural Biology satellite event	Extremely	Yes	Yes	Yes	Extremely	Good	Research infrastructures need international collaboration to ensure the best use of limited resources	No, I did not listen to the interpretation	I did not use the interpretation service
18/06/2021 08:05:00	Portugal	no further comments, it was very good.	Yes	Opportunities in the European Programme	Very	Yes	Yes	Yes	Extremely	Very good	Cooperation	No, I did not listen to the interpretation	I did not use the interpretation service
18/06/2021 08:12:00	Brazil	I liked very much the side events	Yes	The session on Prerequisites for biobanking collaborations and advancements across continents and also the sessions regarding MIRRI	Very	Yes	Yes	Yes	Very	Very good	Interaction and cooperation	No, I did not listen to the interpretation	I did not use the interpretation service
18/06/2021 08:32:00	Brazil	I love the opportunities to send messages with another researchers and the social event time.	Yes	Sharing opportunities	Extremely	Yes	Yes	Yes	Extremely	Excellent	The networks are very important to develop our world.	Yes, I listened to the interpretation in Spanish	Excellent
18/06/2021 12:30:00	Costa Rica	It covered a lot of research areas, so I got a general perspective what type of RIs are available. And also the funding opportunities with Horizon Europe was very interesting, yet a lot of questions remain because this is a very complex funding resource. I work on Bioinformatics, and this area was barely discussed. There are great consortium in Europe regarding this area, for instance Elvar, that should be included in the next symposium.	Yes	The MIRRI sessions were super complete and relevant to the ideas I have in mind. The panel discussions were also very good, insightful about the reality we live in.	Very	No	Yes	Yes	Very	Very good	<p>Some countries are well resourced in terms of RIs in LATAM and have strong connections with Europe. Some LATAM countries could benefit with the development of stronger connections within the region, and as a consequence with Europe.</p> <p>Better legislation and politics has to be developed in other to favor the relationships with Europe.</p>	No, I did not listen to the interpretation	I did not use the interpretation service
18/06/2021 15:33:00	Argentina	1	Yes	9	Very	Yes	Yes	Yes	Extremely	Very good	3	No, I did not listen to the interpretation	I did not use the interpretation service
20/06/2021 21:08:00	Costa Rica	A good deal of information about places and initiatives to collaborate. Opened up the scenario to create LA hubs.	Yes	I took the opportunity to listen to different topics. Due to timetable and other activities of my own, I didn't were able to attend alls groups so it's not fare to pick just one!	Extremely	Yes	Yes	Yes	Extremely	Excellent	Improve collaboration channels!	No, I did not listen to the interpretation	I did not use the interpretation service
21/06/2021 09:30:00	Uruguay	the platform was so easy to use and i really recommend it	Yes	First and fourth day sessions	Very	Yes	Yes	Yes	Very	Very good	Thank you! Looking forward for next events	Yes, I listened to the interpretation in Spanish	Very good
21/06/2021 16:08:00	Uruguay	The symposium had a very good organization and dealt with a very interesting and relevant agenda	Yes	All the sessions had very good quality level. The ones that involved policy makers helped to know policies and path tendencies in both regions.	Very	Yes	Yes	Yes	Very	Excellent	keep on working, still a lot to be don in the latinoamerican region and plenty of opportunities for networking with europe	No, I did not listen to the interpretation	I did not use the interpretation service
07/08/2021 09:11	Portugal	The interdisciplinary	Yes	all	Extremely	Yes	Yes	Yes	Extremely	Excellent	hope in the future	No, I did not listen to the interpretation	I did not use the interpretation service
07/08/2021 09:30	Czech Republic	In general, several organizations had the chance to present their programs	No	There were some issues on research programs	Somewhat	Yes	No	Yes	Very	Very good	There should be more interactions between the representatives of different organizations that support research with the researchers	No, I did not listen to the interpretation	I did not use the interpretation service
07/08/2021 10:26	Uruguay	Very stimulating discussion with decision-makers and politicians.	Yes	Latin american-Europe Bioimaging meeting	Very	No	Yes	Yes	Somewhat	Good	A lot of work to do, mainly to convince decision-makers that we need to discuss more the role of RI in LA.	No, I did not listen to the interpretation	I did not use the interpretation service
07/08/2021 11:18	Colombia	I liked a lot. Interesting sessions and speakers and we hope that the forum continues in the future.	Yes	In general, for me, all sessions.	Very	Yes	Yes	Yes	Very	Very good	The opportunity to join the projects and initiatives to leverage interaction and the scientific community.	No, I did not listen to the interpretation	I did not use the interpretation service
07/08/2021 12:42	Colombia	It was an excellent experience. Have the opportunity to connect with scientists from all over the world, regardless of time or space. Thanks a lot!	Yes	The main conferences.	Extremely	Yes	Yes	Yes	Extremely	Excellent	Limits are in your mind. With a vision of having ideas come true, it is possible becoming them real	No, I did not listen to the interpretation	I did not use the interpretation service
07/09/2021 11:18	United Kingdom	I thought the event was quite well organised and easy to follow	Yes	all of them	Somewhat	Yes	No	Yes	Very	Very good	clear communication	Yes, I listened to the interpretation in English and Spanish	Very good
15/07/2021 04:08:00	France	It was great to hear the perspectives from Latin America and the meeting seemed to spur on a step change in organising and planning amongst countries and institutions. Having the translation option was probably great for many speakers from Latin America to be able to express themselves better but that so many of the EU representatives did the same was disappointing. The chat was very busy but all in Spanish so again not possible to follow for those not able to speak spanish.	No	I was not particularly excited by any of the sessions	Not so	Yes	No	Yes	Very	Very good	That Latin America needs to get more organised before entering into collaboration. To me a lot of the sessions I attended had discussions on how to better organise at the LAC level. I think this also meant that the European participants were less likely to participate in the discussions because there was not much for us to say on that and as mentioned above, it was not possible to follow the chat.	Yes, I listened to the interpretation in English	Very good

LATIN AMERICA-EUROPE SYMPOSIUM ON RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURES

LATIN AMERICA-EUROPE SYMPOSIUM ON RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURES

JUNE 15 - 18, 2021

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whoava app USAGE HIGHLIGHTS

OVERALL DOWNLOAD RATE

62% ATTENDEE DOWNLOAD RATE FOR WHOVA EVENTS
71%

SPEAKERS DOWNLOAD RATE

64% SPEAKERS DOWNLOADED
39 of 61

ATTENDEES LOVED OUR APP

85% TOOK THE SURVEY
11

PROFILE VIEWS IN APP

1055

ATTENDEE NETWORKING

PHOTOS SHARED
92

ANNOUNCEMENT OPEN RATE

72%

ANNOUNCEMENTS VIA IN-APP NOTIFICATIONS AND EMAILS
4

ANNOUNCEMENTS

- The Latin America - Europe Symposiu...
- The Latin America - Europe Symposiu...
- The Latin America - Europe Symposiu...
- Latin America - Europe Symposium Fi...

whoava app COMMUNITY BOARD

DISCUSSION TOPICS POSTED

33

MOST POPULAR DISCUSSION TOPICS

- **Session Q&A**
43 messages
- **Article Sharing**
27 articles shared
- **Exhibitor Showcase**
16 messages
- **Refurbished Lab Equipment for Circular Economy**
16 messages
- **Open Data for Research**
15 messages

COMMUNITY BOARD TOTAL MESSAGES

440

MEET-UP PARTICIPATION

30

MEET-UPS ORGANIZED

1

MOST POPULAR MEET-UPS

- **LatinAmerica and Europe Advanced Comp...**
30 people joined this meet-up

JOB OPENINGS POSTED

11

COMPANIES THAT POSTED

6

COMPANIES THAT POSTED JOBS

Czech Centre for Phenogenomics, BBMRI-ERIC, International Iberian Nanotechnology Laboratory - INL, ECRIN (European Clinical Research Infrastructure Network), European Molecular Biology Laboratory, RNP

Whoava

whova app AGENDA HIGHLIGHTS

AGENDA IN-APP VIEWS

1702

PERSONAL AGENDA SET-UP BY ATTENDEES

174

PERCENTAGE OF ATTENDEES SET
39%

AGENDA SESSIONS MOST POPULAR

SESSION POPULARITY BASED ON LIKES AND PERSONAL AGENDA ADDS

- Expanding Latin American-European partnerships - New Opportunities
8 likes and 90 personal agenda adds
- Panel discussion: Opportunities for Latin American-European collaborations between RIs
4 likes and 51 personal agenda adds
- Research Infrastructure landscapes in Latin America and Europe
1 likes and 65 personal agenda adds
- Opening and Welcome of participants
1 likes and 51 personal agenda adds
- Panel discussion: Future of Latin America-Europe Research Infrastructure Collaborations
48 personal agenda adds

whova app MARKETING TOOLS YOU USED

AGENDA WEBPAGE VIEWS

4557

Your Agenda
Webpage Design
<https://whova.com/embedded/ev...>

REGISTRATION

614

whova app

MOBILE & WEB APP ACTIVE USERS

TOTAL ACTIVE USERS

443

USERS WHO SIGNED IN EITHER MOBILE OR WEB APP

USED BOTH MOBILE & WEB APP

112

USERS WHO DOWNLOADED THE MOBILE AND SIGNED IN TO WEB APP

MOBILE APP ACTIVE USERS

38%

ATTENDEES WHO USED THE MOBILE APP
169/443

WEB APP ACTIVE USERS

77%

ATTENDEES WHO USED THE WEB APP
344/443

who va app
**COMMUNITY
HIGHLIGHTS**

DISCUSSION TOPICS POSTED

33

COMMUNITY BOARD TOTAL MESSAGES

440

ASK ORGANIZERS MESSAGES

25

BREAK-THE-ICE MESSAGES

59

JOB POSTING MESSAGES

11

OTHER CONFERENCES MESSAGES

13

ARTICLE SHARED MESSAGES

23

MOST FOLLOWED DISCUSSIONS

- Session Q&A
17 people followed this topic
- Refurbished Lab Equipment for Circular Economy
13 people followed this topic
- Funding for large-scale RI collaboration
13 people followed this topic

PHOTOS SHARED

60

TOTAL LIKES FOR ALL PHOTOS

63

POPULAR PHOTOS MOST LIKED

MEET-UP PARTICIPATION

30

MEET-UPS ORGANIZED

1

MOST POPULAR MEET-UPS

- LatinAmerica and Europe Advanced Computing Cyberinfrastructures via RedCLARA/SCALAC
30 people joined this meet-up

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ATTENDEE VIEWING ACTIVITY

ATTENDEES WATCHED TOTAL

SESSIONS WITH VIDEO OR STREAM

271

TOTAL DURATION WATCHED
506 HRS

36

WATCHED SESSIONS MOST POPULAR STREAMS

SESSION POPULARITY BASED ON NUMBER OF ATTENDEES

1. Expanding Latin American-European partnerships - New Opportunities
85.2 hours, watched by 113 attendees
2. Opening and Welcome of participants
55.0 hours, watched by 113 attendees
3. Expanding Latin American-European partnerships - New Opportunities
66.7 hours, watched by 90 attendees

WATCHED SESSIONS MOST POPULAR VIDEOS

SESSION POPULARITY BASED ON NUMBER OF ATTENDEES

1. International Conference on Research Infrastructures (ICRI) 2022
0.1 hours, watched by 5 attendees

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NETWORKING HIGHLIGHTS

PRIVATE MESSAGES 1-ON-1

822

PRIVATE GROUP CHATS CREATED

80

ATTENDEE INTERACTION 1-ON-1

716

Attendees who have interacted with each other in private 1-on-1 messages

ATTENDEES INDICATED INTEREST

124

RECOMMENDED ATTENDEES

456

ATTENDEES MATCHED BASED OFF OF INTERESTS, LOCATIONS, AFFILIATION

TOP RECOMMENDATION MATCHES
research infrastructures, bioinformatics, international scientific cooperation, cal, montevide, and more...

BIZ CARD SCANNED AND EXCHANGED

2

ATTENDEES PROFILE VIEWS

1055

whova app ATTENDEE BREAKDOWN

ATTENDEE CATEGORIES

TOP 5 ATTENDEE CATEGORIES

	ATTENDEES
All attendees not in other categories	610
Speakers	52
Exhibitors	22
Organizers	6

ATTENDEE AFFILIATION

TOP 5 ATTENDEE AFFILIATION

	ATTENDEES
Universidad del Valle	19
Institut Pasteur de Montevideo	10
LifeWatch ERIC	10
University of Sao Paulo	9
Instruct-ERIC	8

MOST ACTIVE ATTENDEES

TOP 5 MOST ACTIVE BY APP ACTION

	ACTIONS
Marta Vandrovцова	707
Natalie Haley	609
Viridiana Beltran	478
Alex Moura	370
Claudia Alen Amaro	311

Whova

whova app AGENDA WEBPAGE

YOUR AGENDA WEBPAGE DESIGN

AGENDA WEBPAGE URL

<https://ri-vis.eu/>

WHOVA TEMPLATE USED

MEDITERRANEAN

Agenda

Displaying agenda in event timezone (12:24 PM -03)

Tuesday, June 15

9:00 AM-10:15 AM
Thematic workshops: IS_MIRRI21 virtual events: Matchmaking for Horizon Europe opportunities and MIRRI membership
1 Subsession

10:30 AM-10:45 AM
Opening and Welcome of participants
Live Stream: [Join stream](#)

10:45 AM-11:25 AM
Research Infrastructure landscapes in Latin America and Europe
Live Stream: [Join stream](#)

11:25 AM-12:10 PM
Creating synergies - Towards new EU-LAC RI partnerships
Live Stream: [Join stream](#)
3 Subsessions

12:15 PM-1:30 PM
Case studies of multinational and biregional Latin American-European partnerships
Live Stream: [Join stream](#)
5 Subsessions

1:30 PM-2:00 PM
Wrap up of day 1
Live Stream: [Join stream](#)

2:00 PM-3:00 PM
Sirius virtual visit - a live tour through one of the most advanced synchrotron light sources in the world
Live Stream: [Join stream](#)

Wednesday, June 16

Thursday, June 17

Friday, June 18

TOTAL AGENDA WEBPAGE VIEWS

4557

agenda stats shown are not from the app

INDIVIDUAL AGENDA TOTAL VIEWS

20738

agenda stats shown are not from the app

TOP 10 AGENDAS

1. Strengthening the Structural Biology Community in Latin America
2. Creating synergies – Towards new EU-LAC RI partnerships
3. Case studies of multinational and biregional Latin American-European partnerships
4. Thematic workshops: IS_MIRRI21 virtual events: Matchmaking for Horizon Europe opportunities and MIRRI membership COPY
5. The E-Science European Infrastructure for Biodiversity and Ecosystem Research LifeWatch ERIC
6. Strengthening the Structural Biology Community in Latin America
7. Research Infrastructure landscapes in Latin America and Europe
8. Panel discussion: Future of Latin America-Europe Research Infrastructure Collaborations
9. European Commission
10. Expanding Latin American-European partnerships - New Opportunities

whova app SPEAKER WEBPAGE

YOUR SPEAKER WEBPAGE DESIGN

SPEAKER WEBPAGE URL

https://whova.com/embedded/speakers/rlas_202106/

Speakers

 Alejandro Buschiazzi Institut Pasteur de Montevideo			
 Andres Kamaid Dr. Institut Pasteur de Montevideo			
 Apostolia Karamali EU Commision			
 Claudia Alen Amaro Senior Programme... Instruct-ERIC			
 Damian Refojo Head, Neuroscience... Instituto de Investigación en...			

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YOUR EXHIBITOR WEBPAGE DESIGN

EXHIBITOR WEBPAGE URL

https://whova.com/embedded/exhibitor/rlas_202106/

Print / Download

All Exhibitors

All Exhibitors

BBMRI-ERIC
<http://www.bbMRI-eric.eu/>
BBMRI is a European Research Infrastructure of biobanks and biomolecular resources. For its Member States, it provides expertise

DARIAH
<http://www.dariah.eu>
The Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities (DARIAH) is a distributed Research Infrastructure that supports and enhances digitally-

ECRIN-ERIC
<https://ecrin.org/>
ECRIN's mission is to support the conduct of multinational clinical research in Europe. For this purpose, it support sponsors/investigators to

EMBL
<http://www.embl.org/artise>
ARISE is the Marie Curie Training program implemented by the European Molecular Biology Laboratory at it's 6 locations in

EMBRC
<https://embrc.eu>
EMBRC, the European Marine Biological Resource Centre, is Europe's research infrastructure for marine biological resources and

EMPHASIS
<https://emphasis.plant-phenotyping.eu/>
EMPHASIS is the European infrastructure for plant phenotyping that is aimed at improving food security and agricultural business in a

ESBB

ESS ERIC
<https://www.europeansocialsur...>
The European Social Survey (ESS) is an academically driven cross-national survey that has been conducted across Europe since its establishment

EU-OPENSREEN ERIC
<https://www.eu-openscreen.eu/>
EU-OPENSREEN integrates high-capacity screening platforms throughout Europe, which jointly use a rationally selected compound

Euro-Biolmaging
<http://www.eurobiomaging.eu>
We are the European landmark research infrastructure for biological and biomedical imaging as recognised by the European Strategy

Global Biolmaging
<https://globalbiomaging.org/>
We are the international network of Biolmaging Research Infrastructures and Communities, bringing together, under the coordination of the

ICRI
<https://www.icri2022.cz/>
International Conference on Research Infrastructures, a global forum encouraging cooperation and discussion on matters of international

Instruct
<http://instruct-eric.org>
Instruct-ERIC is the single point of

IS_MIRRI21 project
<https://ismirri21.miri.org/>
IS_MIRRI21 is a European

whova app EVENT WEBSITE

YOUR EVENT WEBSITE DESIGN

EVENT WEBSITE URL

https://whova.com/web/rlas_202106/

HOME SPEAKERS AGENDA EXHIBITORS SPONSORS DOCUMENTS REGISTER

Latin America-Europe Symposium on Research Infrastructures

JUN 15 - 18, 2021

REGISTER

0 DAYS 0 HOURS 0 MINUTES 0 SECONDS

INTRODUCTION

The Latin America-Europe Symposium on Research Infrastructures, organised by RI-VIS and EU-LAC ResInfra, will bring together delegates from Latin American and European research infrastructures (RIs), science policy organisations and research institutions to discuss opportunities and challenges for RI cooperations between Latin America and Europe.

International cooperation in science and technology is an important part of addressing major global issues like climate change, infectious disease, food security, and natural disasters. Research Infrastructures are organizations providing state-of-the-art resources, services and expertise to scientists. The RI-VIS project unites research infrastructures across scientific domains in order to work together more efficiently and effectively and increase their visibility in society at large.

Research Infrastructures provide such coordination by offering access to key facilities, resources and expertise to empower research driven by scientific excellence and beyond the individual research capacity of different countries, economic sectors, or institutions.

The Latin America-Europe Symposium on Research Infrastructures, organised by RI-VIS and EU-LAC ResInfra, will bring together delegates from Latin American and European research infrastructures (RIs).

We also invite representatives from funding agencies as well as policy makers to join and discuss opportunities for working together. By bringing together the right people we hope to create collaborations and initiate networks in a sustainable way so that all stakeholders benefit.

The RI-VIS and EU-LAC ResInfra projects share common goals to build sustainable partnerships in research infrastructure between Europe and Latin America and the Caribbean.

In anticipation of the upcoming event, a White Paper 'Recommendations towards cooperation between Latin American and European research infrastructures' has been published, collating the insights of experts from Latin American RIs, European RIs, and policymakers. Key findings from the white paper will be discussed at the symposium.

We are looking forward to e-meeting you soon,

Bahne Stechmann, EU-OPENSREEN & RI-VIS Immaculada Figueroa, EU-LAC ResInfra Coordinator
 Viridiana Beltran Venegas, BMMRI & RI-VIS Sabina Guaylupo, EU-LAC ResInfra Project Manager
 Claudia Alén Amaro, Instruct & RI-VIS Claudia Romano, UY MEC

DOWNLOAD EVENT APP

Follow Us!

Speakers

LATIN AMERICA-EUROPE SYMPOSIUM ON RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURES

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TICKETS WHOVA SOLD

614

YOUR REGISTRATION PAGE

REGISTRATION URL

https://whoava.com/portal/registration/rlas_202106/

Whoava
registration

Latin America-Europe Symposium on Research Infrastructures

June 15 - 18, 2021 (-03)

Ticket

General Admission 0

Sales end: 2021-07-02T00:00:00 (America/Sao_Paulo)

[Register](#)

Event Description

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Bahne Stechmann, EU-OPENSREEN & RI-VIS	Inmaculada Figueroa, EU-LAC ResInfra Coordinator
Viridiana Beltran Venegas, BBMRI & RI-VIS	Sabina Guaylupo, EU-LAC ResInfra Project Manager
Claudia Alén Amaro, Instruct & RI-VIS	Claudia Romano, UY MEC

LATIN AMERICA-EUROPE SYMPOSIUM ON RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURES

whova app EXHIBITOR REPORT

EXHIBITOR BOOTH STATS

VISITS	LIKES	COMMENTS
57	2	0

BBMRI-ERIC

VISITS	LIKES	COMMENTS
17	0	0

DARIAH

VISITS	LIKES	COMMENTS
13	0	0

ECRIN-ERIC

VISITS	LIKES	COMMENTS
13	1	0

EMBL

VISITS	LIKES	COMMENTS
22	2	1

EMBRIC

VISITS	LIKES	COMMENTS
22	2	1

EMPHASIS

VISITS	LIKES	COMMENTS
13	0	0

ESBB

VISITS	LIKES	COMMENTS
24	2	0

ESS ERIC

VISITS	LIKES	COMMENTS
23	6	0

EU-OPENSREEN ERIC

VISITS	LIKES	COMMENTS
10	3	0

Euro-Biolmaging

VISITS	LIKES	COMMENTS
8	2	0

Global Biolmaging

VISITS	LIKES	COMMENTS
21	4	0

ICRI

VISITS	LIKES	COMMENTS
21	3	0

Instruct

VISITS	LIKES	COMMENTS
38	4	0

IS_MIRRI21 project

LATIN AMERICA-EUROPE SYMPOSIUM ON RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURES

Whova

ADDED VIDEOS TOTAL

11

ADDED LIVE SHOWCASES TOTAL

1

EXHIBITOR PHOTOS UPLOADED

 1 👍					
 1 👍					
 1 👍					

USERS CLAIMED RAFFLE

15